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PROCEDURE FOR PLANNING A SPEAKING LESSON IN ACCORDANCE WITH CELTA GUIDELINES

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Abstract

The process of teaching how to develop speaking skills in English and how to learn it is a vital part of an English classroom. The article gives a description of a speaking lesson stages preparation and ensures efficient lesson outcomes in case of a proper planning and self – reflection on its completion.

Keywords: Lesson planning, main and subsidiary aims and objectives, skills lesson, lesson outcomes, classroom management, pre-teaching blocking vocabulary, freer practice, feedback on content, feedback on language.

A significant part of English teaching-learning system is lesson planning, which is a step-by-step guide that provides a structure for an essential learning. The plan aids the teacher to choose the materials, adapt and tailor the activities to student's needs, be prepared for possible problems and challenges [1]. An efficient lesson plan has three basic components: aims and objectives of the course, teaching and learning activities and, assessments to check student's understanding of the topic.

Some teachers with experience seem to have an ability to think on their feet, and this allows them to believe that lesson planning is unnecessary. However, most teachers do not share this view and prepare their lessons. The resulting lesson plans range from the very formal and elaborate to a few hurried notes. But even the notes are still a plan of a kind [2]. First of all, a teacher has to identify the type of the lesson to teach: skills lesson (listening, reading, writing or speaking) or

systems (vocabulary, grammar, functions or pronunciation). So, according to lesson outcomes that is planned to achieve by the end of the lesson, we identify the main aims, subsidiary aims and personal aims [3]. For instance, the main aim of speaking lesson: students will have developed their speaking skills in the context of suggestions for laws, by means of useful phrases for presenting new laws and giving opinions of agreement and disagreement. Subsidiary aims: students will have practised their listening skills for gist/specific information about a suggestion of new laws, identifying useful phrases, will have developed oral fluency on the topic of 'Law' (for instance, 'Drivers should have a trial driving licence for a couple of years before they are allowed to have a full license. They should only get a full licence if they have shown that they are safe on the road'). Personal aims are identified based on teacher's strengths and weaknesses, for example, to be consistent in monitoring, to give clear instructions, to improve

boardwork, to allow more time for a feedback and others.

Secondly, the teacher has to anticipate problems, therefore it is required to list any potential problems for learners with classroom management and skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) in our case with speaking in particular. Predict how you would deal with potential problems arisen with classroom management. As an example, there might be an odd number of students, which will make pair work a little problematic. The solution will be to nominate some students to work in a group of three as a result they will have equal speaking opportunities. There will probably be fast finishers and it is crucial to monitor attentively and provide them with extra tasks. For weaker students we have to apply scaffolding technique that is to use some template prompts, sentence frames, create mindmaps, graphs and tables. Lexis might also be a challenge that is why it is mandatory to pre-teach blocking vocabulary in a student - centered way.

In addition, to generate student's interest at a warm-up or lead-in stages, it is useful to prompt any pictures, visuals, bring realia, ask some questions, have a discussion, watch a short video/podcast, listen to some short excerpts of music. It is also a good idea to prepare questions before introducing the main topic of the lesson as you deepen into the topic, hand out prepared materials.

The speaking lesson plan comprises the following stages [4]:

1. Lead -in – to generate interest in the topic, set topic.
2. Vocabulary pre-teaching – to pre-teach any key vocabulary by focusing on meaning (ways of conveying it, concept checking questions), pronunciation (features of connected speech, strong, weak forms, linking, elision etc.) and form (part of speech).
3. Reading or listening (optional) – to provide a model of the text type.
4. Focus on the layout – to present/ elicit the layout.
5. Focus on the language -to present or elicit the vocabulary.
6. Freer practice - for students to provide their own speaking.
7. Feedback on content – to evaluate speaking.
8. Feedback on language – to provide error correction, highlight examples of good language.

Finally, upon completion of a speaking lesson plan writing we have to make sure:

1. The procedure reflects speaking type we are supposed to teach.
2. The procedure aims to contribute to the main lesson achievement in a relatively coherent manner.
3. Stages of the lesson have smooth transitions.
4. To allocate enough time for each stage.
5. To allocate enough time to provide feedback, answer students' questions.
6. To implement various interaction patterns such as individual, pair work, group work, whole class so that the lesson is not monotonous.
7. To have Plan 'B', if the lesson goes not the way it is planned as you are supposed to teach students not the plan.
8. To provide feedback after each activity.
9. To vary quiet and lively activities.
10. To establish a positive end of the lesson [3, 4].

In conclusion, a speaking lesson has to be deliberately planned, therefore teachers have to systematically focus on each lesson stage and develop appropriate materials, tasks and activities for learners [5]. By planning lessons according to the stages in the Teaching Speaking Template, teacher will be able to provide an engaging and meaningful input by means of valuable scaffolding and guidance to improve learners' performance.

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